

Strength and toughness: the challenging case of TaC-based composites

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ABSTRACT

This work aims at studying the relationships between strength and toughness of tantalum carbide (TaC) ceramics, a refractory ceramic used in aerospace and energy production sectors. The effect of different secondary phases was explored: (I) the addition of a transition metal silicide with suited thermo-elastic properties, TaSi₂, (II) the addition of SiC particles, platelets or fibers, and (III) chopped carbon fibers. Microstructural analyses, performed by scanning and transmission electron microscopy, were essential in revealing at nanoscale level the morphological changes occurred during sintering in the reinforcing phase and its interaction with matrix and sintering additive. Mechanisms of reinforcement evolution are suggested accordingly. Fracture toughness and flexural strength were measured and the values were compared to unreinforced materials and discussed in agreement to the microstructural features. Strength approaching 1 GPa was obtained upon addition of SiC particles, but residual thermal stresses prevented from notable increase of toughness, which fluctuated around 4 MPa·√m. A good compromise between strength and toughness was found for addition of Hi-Nicalon SiC fiber, 550 MPa and 5.3 MPa·√m, respectively. More refractory SiC fibers resulted not effective, owing to the rising of tensional state in the matrix. On the other hand, TaSi₂ led to a toughness of 4.7 MPa·√m and strength around 680 MPa. Conversely, carbon fiber led to poor toughness due to unfavorable combination of coefficient of thermal expansion with the matrix.

Keywords: A. Ceramic-matrix composites (CMCs); A. Discontinuous reinforcement; B. Fracture toughness; B. Strength; D. Electron microscopy.

1. Introduction

The carbides of the group IV-VI transition metals have extremely high melting points (3000-4000°C) and are commonly referred to as “ultra-refractory carbides”. Beside their stability at high temperatures, these compounds also possess high hardness, thus finding industrial use in cutting tools and wear-resistant parts [1,2]. In particular

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tantalum carbide (TaC) is an emerging material for use in the propulsion sector, where thermal solicitations are active, but the environment is reducing, so the pesting oxidation featuring the carbides is not the main issue [3]. On the contrary, thermal shock resistance and low damage tolerance are two impelling problems. In this respect, this work is focussed on methods for improving the fracture toughness of TaC-based composites. TaC is known to have a more metallic nature, compared to other covalent compounds like Zr- and Hf-carbides, thanks to the d-shell containing one electron more [4] and this generally results in less brittle materials. As most of refractory ceramics, TaC can achieve high strength values, up to 900 MPa [5], but still too moderate toughness to allow a safe use in various application fields.

In this work, different approaches were explored, mainly through addition of reinforcing phases as suggested by previous works: metal disilicide particles with suitable thermo-elastic properties [5], SiC particles [6], SiC platelets [7], SiC fibers [8,9] and C fibers [10]. Results are compared to unreinforced matrices, with and without sintering aids.

Transition metal disilicides (MeSi_2) were added to **Zr-, Hf- and Ta- borides and carbides** mainly with the purpose of densification [5,11]. They cannot be considered as solely sintering aids because they significantly modify the microstructure and properties especially when their content is raised over some 5 vol% [5,11]. SiC addition to TaC was tested by Liu et al., who reported fracture toughness overpassing $6 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ for addition of 20 vol% SiC particles [6]. As for platelets, one possible approach to introduce this kind of reinforcement is to exploit the $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ SiC polytypic transformation enabling to pass from rounded particles to platelets, as previously experimented for ZrB_2 -composites [7]. Addition of chopped fibers gave promising results in the case of borides [8,9].

When fiber or platelets were added, the sintering additive had to be accurately selected. TaSi_2 was used to decrease the densification temperature of TaC [5] and inhibit SiC fiber damages [12]. However this additive, and silicides in general, cannot be used in combination with C fiber owing to an excessive reaction leading to the fiber degeneration into SiC agglomerates, therefore Si_3N_4 was employed. Lastly, MoSi_2 was used to promote transient liquid phase sintering of TaC matrix and enable $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ SiC transformation without leaving glassy amorphous phase [7]. Also in this case, TaSi_2 could not be used owing to its volatility in reducing environment at high temperatures and low pressure [5].

The purpose of this study is hence to explore the addition of suitable secondary phases able to trigger efficient toughening mechanisms. Specifically, the effect of the introduction of secondary phases in form of particle, platelet or fiber to TaC matrix will be discussed in relationship to the microstructure evolution and the resulting mechanical properties.

2. Experimental procedure

The ceramic materials produced and the unreinforced reference ceramics are listed in Table 1, together with sintering parameters and main microstructural features. The following commercial powders were used: cubic TaC (Treibacher Industrie AG, Althofen, Austria), mean particle size 1.1 μm ; hexagonal TaSi₂ (ABCR GmbH & Co., Karlsruhe, Germany), particle size < 45 μm ; tetragonal MoSi₂ (Aldrich, Germany), specific surface area 1.60 m²/g, mean particle size 1 μm , impurities: 1 wt% O; α -Si₃N₄ Baysind (Bayer, Germany), specific surface area 12.2 m²/g, impurities: 1.5 wt% O, mean particle size 0.15 μm ; β -SiC (Starck BF-12, Germany), specific surface area 11-13 m²/g, impurities: 0.88 wt% O mean particle size 0.60 μm .

Fibers used as reinforcing phase are displayed in Fig. 1. Hi-Nicalon chopped fibers (COI Ceramics Inc., Magna, USA), with composition (wt%) Si:C:O= 63.7:35.8:0.5, belong to the 2nd generation SiC fibers, have an average diameter of 15 μm and 500 μm length, and are constituted by 55% of β -SiC nano crystals, 40% of Si-C-O amorphous metastable phase and 5% graphite [13]. As a consequence of high amount of amorphous phase they have a smooth aspect in Fig. 1a. Tyranno SA3 (UBE Industries, Ltd., Kogushi, Japan) with composition (wt%) Si:C = 67:31, O<1, Al<2, belongs instead to the 3rd generation, underwent a pyrolysis process above 1800°C enabling partial sintering and the achievement of nearly stoichiometric Si:C ratio [14]. After chopping, the average length of Tyranno SA3 fiber was 100-300 μm , with a stochastic nature of the diameter, from 5 to 8 μm . SEM image of Fig. 1b shows that these fibers have a rough surface and are characterized by SiC crystallites with rounded shape and dimensions around 70 nm, surrounded by carbon-rich dark pockets. The fracture is mainly intergranular, owing to the presence of carbon itself acting as weak interphase. The carbon fiber used as reinforcement for TaC is depicted in Fig. 1c, with average diameter of 7 μm and a chopped length around 250 μm . No mechanical properties are available for this fiber type.

The powder mixtures were ultrasonicated and milled for 24 h in absolute ethanol using silicon carbide milling media, subsequently dried in a rotary evaporator and deagglomerated. Pellets were linearly pressed and subsequently cold isostatically pressed under a 350 MPa pressure. For ceramics containing fibers, the sintering was preceded by a desizing cycle in a graphite furnace at 500°C for 1 h holding time, with a heating rate of 50°C/h under flowing argon. The pellets were then either hot pressed in low vacuum (~100 Pa) using an induction-heated graphite die with an uniaxial pressure of 30 MPa during the heating and increased up to 50 MPa at the maximum temperature, or pressureless sintered in a resistance-heated graphite furnace under a flowing argon atmosphere (~0.1 MPa). The

maximum sintering temperature during hot pressing was set on the basis of the shrinkage curve. Free cooling followed. The schedule of each sintering run is reported in Table 1.

After sintering, the bulk densities were measured by Archimedes method. The microstructures were polished with diamond paste to 0.25 μm and were analyzed with scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Carl Zeiss Sigma NTS GmbH, Oberkochen, Germany) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS, X-Act, INCA Energy 300, Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK). Mean matrix grain size, amount of porosity and amount of secondary phases were determined on micrographs of polished sections using image analysis (Image-Pro Analyzer 7.0, Media Cybernetics, Silver Spring, MD, Rockville, USA). TEM samples were prepared by cutting 3 mm discs from the sintered pellets. These were mechanically ground down to about 15 μm and then further ion beam thinned until small perforations were observed by optical microscopy. Local phase analysis was performed using transmission electron microscopy (FEI Tecnai F20 ST), with an acceleration voltage of 200 keV, equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray system (EDAX EDS X-ray spectrometer PV9761) with super ultra-thin window.

Fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) was evaluated using chevron notched beams (CNB) in flexure. The test bars, 25 x 2 x 2.5 mm³ (length by width by thickness, respectively), were notched with a 0.1 mm-thick diamond saw; the chevron-notch tip depth and average side length were about 0.12 mm and 0.80 mm of the bar thickness, respectively. The specimens were fractured using a semi-articulated silicon carbide four-point fixture with a lower span of 20 mm and an upper span of 10 mm using a screw-driven load frame (Instron mod. 6025, Instron, High Wycombe, GB). The specimens, three for each composite, were loaded with a crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min. The “slice model” equation of Munz et al. [15] was used to calculate K_{Ic} . On the same machine and with the same fixture, the flexural strength (σ) was measured at room temperature; for each material at least five chamfered bars with dimensions 25x2.5x2 mm³ were tested.

3. Results

3.2 *Microstructure of TaC-based ceramics*

3.2.1 *Baseline materials*

An additive free pure TaC ceramic was prepared as reference value (T). As expected, TaC was only 94% dense after sintering at 1900°C for 15 min. The microstructure was spatially uniform and consisted of faceted equiaxed grains with mean grain dimensions in the range of 5-7 μm (Fig. 2a). Occasionally, oxide phases were detected along the grain boundaries and residual porosity ~5 vol % was confirmed. In order to enable complete densification, 5 vol%

Si₃N₄ was added to TaC (Fig. 2b). The sintering temperature for this composite (TS) was 1850°C held for 10 min. The ceramic resulted fully dense with rounded grain size of about 2.5 μm and around 5 vol% SiC particles in place of Si₃N₄, owing to its decomposition in the hot pressing chamber.

3.2.2 Reinforced materials

TaC – SiC particles (TS-S) – Despite the addition of Si₃N₄ as sintering additive, this ceramic required 1850°C to achieve full density. A picture of the polished section is shown in in Fig. 2c. The sintering additive was difficult to detect in the final microstructure, as it reacted with the carbide to form additional SiC phase, giving a final total amount of SiC around 20 vol%. Agglomeration of SiC particles was frequent, but the size of these agglomerates was around 1.5-2.0 μm, i.e. in the order of TaC mean grain size, Table 1.

TaC-TaSi₂ (TT) – This composite, was densified at 1750°C and SEM observation confirmed a pore-less microstructure (Fig. 2d). TaC had mean grain size around 2.5 μm with larger grains, up to 6-7 μm. TaSi₂ grains tended to form large pockets as wide as 3-8 μm. Other spurious phases formed upon decomposition of the additive and were identified as SiC, Si-C-O and SiO₂ and Ta_xSi_yC_z [5].

TaC – SiC platelets (TM-S) – Pressureless sintering of TaC-MoSi₂ system generally requires a temperature around 1950°C [11], but in this case it was set at 2100°C for 3 h in order to let the β→α SiC polytypic transformation to completely occur. The pellet resulted almost fully dense, around 97%, but the mean grain size of TaC was notably coarsened, around 7 μm, with grains up to 16 μm. SiC showed the typical elongated shape of α-polytype and the platelets were homogeneously distributed in the matrix. Residual MoSi₂ phase was found in amount below 3 vol%, in grey contrast and low dihedral angles. SiC platelets were often flanked by triangular secondary phases containing Co traces, owing to powder impurities, or based on silicon, owing to the high sintering temperature favorable to MoSi₂ dissociation, Fig. 3a. TEM analysis confirmed the presence of both phases adjacent to SiC, especially when two platelets were in contact, Fig. 3b,c. SiC-SiC and TaC-SiC interfaces were however found to be non-wetted (Fig. 3d and Fig. 3e,f, respectively), as previously found for similar systems containing SiC and MoSi₂ [7].

TaC – Hi-Nicalon (TT-HN) – The composites containing SiC Hi-Nicalon chopped fiber and sintered with 10 vol% TaSi₂ was fully densified at 1750°C. In the polished section it was observed that no fiber agglomeration occurred and the fibers were distributed almost isotropically in the section plane perpendicular to the hot pressing direction, however their diameter was notably decreased, as the SiC core was around 7 μm compared to the initial diameter of 15 μm; the same occurred on the longitudinal direction, which was reduced to 80 μm-length from the 500 μm initial

length. In the cross section of Fig. 4a, an inner SiC core with irregular boundary can be recognized; moving outwards, TaC bright particles as small as 300 nm and coarsened SiC constitute a jagged rim. Beyond this layer, another 2 μm bright stratum of coarser TaC grains is found, in turn surrounded by coarse SiC platelets with squared shape and grain size around 2-4 μm . TEM images disclosed the fiber morphology in more details, Fig. 4b,c: SiC crystallites in the core were up to 30 nm (Fig. 4c) and immersed in partially amorphous phase and turbostratic carbon (Fig. 4d). The interface between core and rim was separated by constellation of TaC particles, which tended to coalesce, Fig. 4e, and coarsened SiC grains, around 300 nm. Not far from the fiber, α -SiC platelets were found, standing adjacent SiO₂-based glass containing Ta traces, Fig. 4f.

TaC – Tyranno SA3 (TT-T) - This composite was sintered at 1700°C with addition of TaSi₂ and reached a relative density of 97%. The matrix mean grain size is around 2 μm and porosity is almost absent. The fibers were well dispersed in the matrix and the maximum fiber length was 200 μm with fiber debris scattered throughout the matrix. Large areas of TaSi₂, light gray phase with dimension 6-7 μm , were also observed in the matrix; occasionally these were intergranularly micro-cracked. Other secondary phases were SiC/Si-C-O and SiO₂ deriving both from the additive dissociation and from fiber. Indeed, the fiber/matrix adhesion was good, owing to silica-based zones at the matrix/fiber interface, Fig. 5a. As for the reinforcement morphology, Tyranno fiber maintained an appearance closer to the pristine aspect, as compared to the Hi-Nicalon fiber. Coalescence of SiC crystallites took place in the rim, about 1.3 μm thick, leaving about 40% of the fiber with typical features of Tyranno SA3 fibers, i.e. dark carbon-rich phase among SiC crystallites. TEM images of the central and outer regions of the fiber are shown in Fig. 5b,c. The difference between SiC crystallites in the core and in the fiber periphery was minor, around 110 nm in the core and around 120 nm in the rim, but both coarsened as compared to the starting 70 nm, and also little differences in the amount of amorphous phase could be detected by electron diffraction. The space between the crystallites in the core, was filled by carbon-rich partially amorphous phase, Fig. 5d, whilst in the rim, mostly clean junctions were found among SiC grains, Fig. 5e. On the contrary, the fiber/matrix interface was often wetted by Si-C-O glass, Fig. 5f.

TaC – Carbon fiber (TS-C) – This composite was sintered at 1800°C and reached a relative density around 98%. The sintering additive, Si₃N₄, tended to react with the carbide matrix and the fiber and was mostly converted to SiC which was found spread throughout the matrix and at the TaC-fiber interface. An example of the fiber cross section is shown in Fig. 6a, where it can be seen that carbon branches started to depart from the fiber and incorporate either TaC or SiC grains. Graphitization of some regions of the fiber external part occurred and graphite pockets were occasionally found among TaC grains, Fig. 6b. TEM analyses revealed that the fiber almost lost its PAN-derived

structure, graphite reflections were recognizable in the diffraction pattern of Fig. 6c, but a lot of amorphous phase is present too. High resolution images of the fiber-TaC interfaces showed mainly non-wetted grain boundaries, Fig. 6d-f.

As for the fracture surface of the fiber and platelets composites, all of them showed interesting features, Fig. 7. For example, the fracture surface of in-situ grown SiC platelets, augmented the intergranular characteristics of the ceramic, Fig. 7a. Then in the case of Hi-Nicalon fiber, Fig. 7b, fibers pullout was easily found even if a continuous rough layer surrounds the fibers. It seems that, in this case, the wide interface reaction phase was weakly bonded to the matrix and helped the fibers pullout, but at the same time diffused fibers degeneration occurred. In the case of Tyranno SA3, Fig. 7c, the fibers were generally cut across, but also in this case it was not difficult to find some protruding fiber. Finally, when C fibers were added, carbon acted as weak interphase and fiber pullout or tearing were frequent, as Fig. 7d shows.

3.2 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of the composites are plotted in Fig.8. It can be rapidly noticed that the fracture toughness and strength are dependent on the type of reinforcing agent used. Fracture toughness ranges from 3.7 to 5.3 MPa·√m, Fig. 8a, whilst the strength ranges from 345 to 900 MPa, Fig. 8b. When solely Si₃N₄ was used as additive, TS, notably higher strength was obtained, exceeding 900 MPa, and the results were not significantly different from the addition of 15 vol% of SiC particles (TS-S), just the standard deviation increased owing to particulate agglomeration. As for the other composites, the strength passed from 680 MPa for TT material, to 550 MPa for the Hi-Nicalon fiber-containing composite, which is a decrease of less than 20%, and to 430 MPa for the Tyranno fiber-containing composites, that is a decrease around 34%. Compared to the ZrB₂-composites containing 20 vol% of fiber, the strength decrease was in the order of 30-50% [8,9]. For the present composites, the lower strength reduction in the case of Hi-Nicalon fibers could be related to the multiple effect of a coarser TaC matrix, 3-7 μm, of a fibers thinning from 200 to 50 μm length and of the formation of SiC particulates of dimension around 10 μm, which is not extremely different from the dimension of TaC grains, fibers and the newly formed SiC particles. It follows that the fibers did not result so extremely bigger than the matrix and hence they did not constitute a defect population like it happened for the ZrB₂-based composites. However, in the case of carbon fiber addition, the strength decrease was definitely more dramatic, as it passed from to 340 MPa for a volume of fiber of 15%, with a net decrease of 62%.

4. Discussion

4.1 Reinforcements evolution and interactions with the matrix

SiC platelets – The formation of SiC platelets is a consequence of prolonged thermal treatment at temperature above 1900°C enabling the $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ SiC polytypic transformation. MoSi₂ was selected as sintering aid in view of its role in favoring the densification through formation of transient liquid phases and of its refractoriness at high temperature [5,11]. Little amount of liquid phases formed at 2010°C, owing to the eutectic between MoSi₂ and SiC [16], certainly helped the local rearrangement and agglomeration of SiC rounded particles and favored their evolution to platelets leaving clean grain boundaries with the matrix. According to the model proposed by Xu et al. [17], α -SiC nucleates heterogeneously at twin boundaries, stacking faults and twins, as these planar faults resemble local regions of α -SiC and therefore facilitate its nucleation. As thermal treatment proceeded, coarsening of SiC grains occurred by dissolution of the smaller β -SiC particles into the liquid and re-precipitation on the β/α -SiC composite grain along the α -SiC side, owing to its higher stability at these temperature and higher growth rate as compared to that on the β -SiC regions. A sketch of the evolution of SiC particle to platelet during sintering is depicted in Fig. 9a.

Hi-Nicalon fiber – Comparing Fig. 1a and 4a, it is evident that remarkable reactions took place during sintering in presence of TaSi₂, even if the maximum temperature was relatively low, 1750°C. Similar sintering temperature were used for borides reinforced with the same SiC chopped fibers, but these resulted much less damaged [8], therefore TaSi₂ and the carbide matrix seem to be responsible for the more pronounced fibers degeneration. The instability of such kind of fiber is mainly due to the amorphous Si-C-O phase, decomposing above 1500°C into SiO/CO and SiC [18], and to the presence of free turbostratic carbon; SiC nanocrystallites just tend to coarsen when exposed to high temperature.

The resulting fiber aspect is a combination of several factors. First TaSi₂ easily dissociates in reducing environment according to (1), favorable above 1100°C [5]:

The formation of silicon, which is liquid at 1415°C, is very close to the onset of densification for this composite. The decrease of TaSi₂ content after sintering and the presence of Si-based phases in the final microstructure are consistent with the occurrence of reaction (1). The formation of SiC particles could derive from the carburization of silicon according to (2):

Other important players are the moving species in the fibers: C and Si-C-O. It is very probable that Ta-Si species and Si-C-O strongly interacted at the fiber/matrix interface, and that further Ta-Si phases were reduced to TaC by free carbon moving outwards from the fiber core, forming additional SiC. Possible reactions are then (3) and (4):

In addition, SiC crystallites of the fibers coarsened and provoked the fibers deformation and aperture. The coarse SiC particles which form a sort of crown surrounding the first TaC-ring might have origin from the liquid Si squeezed out from the fiber, which was carbo-reduced to SiC by the reducing atmosphere. A sketch of the evolution of Hi-Nicalon fiber during sintering is depicted in Fig. 9b.

Tyranno SA3 fiber – This type of fiber is more refractory and therefore more stable during sintering, SiC crystallites are coarser, less oxygen is present, only small amount of partially amorphous Si-C and intergranular carbon were found among the crystallites [14]. As a consequence, the differences between raw and sintered fiber, Fig.1b and 5a, are not so dramatic as for Hi-Nicalon fiber. In the sintered fiber no particles were embedded into the fiber, just the outer part was C depleted and denser. SiCO-based glass pockets found at the interface can be due again to the reaction between TaSi₂ and its by-products and the partially amorphous Si-C phase. A sketch of the evolution of Tyranno SA3 fiber during sintering is depicted in Fig. 9c.

C fiber – Carbon fiber retained its shape close to the original one, Fig.1c and 6a. No continuous SiC crown formed between fiber and matrix, just the fiber edges were irregularly open after reaction with silicon nitride to form silicon carbide and graphite, according to (5):

The evolution of nitrogen is probably responsible for lower densification kinetics as compared to TaSi₂, owing to the increased viscosity of the Si-based liquid phase [19]. Clean grain boundaries enabled fiber pullout, especially in the areas where SiC was not present. The intrinsic change of the PAN fibers morphology may have compromised their mechanical properties. The evolution of carbon fiber during sintering is sketched in Fig. 9d.

4.2 *Effect of secondary phases on fracture toughness and strength trade off*

Bar plots of fracture toughness and strength in Fig. 8 evidence some differences amongst the composites analyzed and show that in most cases there is some tradeoff between these two properties.

Several can be the toughening mechanisms taking place in composites: (I) pinning when the crack front bows in the matrix and remains pinned at the particles or fibers, (II) crack deflection or branching when the crack meets an obstacle and bifurcates or follows a more tortuous path reducing the stress intensity at the crack tip, (III) micro-cracking when the misfit between thermal expansion coefficients introduces a stress field which can produce spontaneous micro-cracks thus adsorbing energy during the fracture, (IV) crack bridging when the front of the crack passes beyond the reinforcing phase leaving it intact and bridging the fracture surfaces in the wake of the crack and (V) residual stress toughening if the particles have a higher thermal expansion coefficient than the matrix and create compressive local stress field in the matrix thus decreasing the stress intensity factor.

As for this last mechanism, thermal residual stresses in composites naturally arise owing to the coupling of different phases with different thermo-elastic properties. The magnitude of the residual stresses depends on the difference of elastic properties and coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between matrix and reinforcements multiplied by the temperature difference at which elastic stresses develop (ΔT). The proper evaluation of these tensile stresses in the matrix becomes particularly important when high temperature composites are considered, since ΔT for these types of composites is high enough to generate residual stresses in the order of the tensile strength of matrix itself. The evaluation of residual stresses in such types of composites is tricky and the results are not always in agreement with each other depending on the technique used. Measurements of residual stresses were performed through neutron diffraction, Raman spectroscopy and x-ray diffraction in ZrB_2 -SiC composites [20,21] and pointed out that stresses begin to accumulate at $\sim 1400^\circ\text{C}$ during cooling from the processing temperature. Because of the fact that the CTE of the TaC matrix, $7.1 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$, [22] is higher than that of SiC particles or fibers ($3.5 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ for Hi-Nicalon fiber [14], $4.5 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ for Tyranno SA3 fiber [14] and particles [23]), and even higher than that of carbon fibers, $2.5 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ [24], as the composites are cooled from their final densification temperature, $1750\text{-}1900^\circ\text{C}$, TaC tends to shrink faster than the SiC/C particles or fibers. **The result is a tensile stress state in the matrix, σ_m , and a corresponding compressive stress state in the reinforcing phases, σ_r , as calculated with Taya et al.'s model using the following relationships [25], plotted in Fig. 10.**

$$\sigma_r = -\frac{(1-f)\varepsilon^*}{f} \sigma_m \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_m = E_m \frac{2f\beta\varepsilon^*}{(1-f)(\beta+2)(1+\nu_m) + 3\beta f(1-\nu_m)} \quad (7)$$

where f is the reinforcement volumetric fraction and

$$\beta = \frac{1 + \nu_m}{1 - 2\nu_r} \frac{E_r}{E_m} \quad (8)$$

E_r , E_m , ν_r and ν_m are Young's modulus and Poisson ratio of reinforcement and matrix, respectively, and ε^* is the thermal expansion misfit strain given by:

$$\varepsilon^* = (\alpha_r - \alpha_m)\Delta T \quad (9)$$

where the α_r , α_m are the thermal expansion coefficients of reinforcement and matrix, respectively and ΔT is the temperature at which stresses begin to accumulate, set as 1400°C [21].

In the materials at hand, in most of the cases, the combination of TaC with the secondary phase implies a negative contribution to toughness due to the residual tensile stress in the matrix. The only case where the opposite conditions are verified is the combination of TaC with TaSi₂, which has a CTE of 8.2·10⁻⁶K⁻¹ [26]. This material has in fact higher fracture toughness than other TaC matrices, T or TS. The plot in Fig. 10 further evidences that tensile stress in the matrix increases increasing the amount of SiC particles (74 MPa in TS and 311 in TS-S) and also passing from partially amorphous fiber to a sintered one (148 MPa in TT-HN to 218 in TT-T). The worst case is the addition of C fiber which leaves a tensile stress of 477 MPa in the matrix.

In order to understand if any positive contribute to toughness is active in the present ceramics, 98.1 N load indentations were introduced onto the polished surface to study the interaction of a slow advancing crack with the microstructure of the composites. Examples of this interaction are shown in Fig. 11.

The crack propagation in pure TaC (material T) is mainly intergranular, Fig. 11a, and its properties are mainly affected by its residual porosity and large grain size. Thus the addition of a sintering aid such as Si₃N₄ has the effect to improve the densification, to decrease the matrix mean grain size and to introduce small amount of SiC particles (material TS). As a consequence, the fracture toughness of TS is slightly higher than that of T, but its strength benefits of an increase of about 50% passing from 580 MPa to 890 MPa, Fig. 8b.

The addition of SiC particles to TS (material TS-S) does not produce further improvement either in strength or toughness. The crack path in Fig. 11b shows that SiC particles efficiently deflect the crack, so it is possible that the expected toughening contribution which derives from a larger quantity of the SiC phase is counterbalanced by the negative effect of increasing the residual tensile matrix stresses, Fig. 10.

The use of TaSi₂ as sintering aid (material TT) produces a different situation: the resulting composite is the only material with the TaC matrix under residual compressive stress, Fig. 10. The toughness is increased from 3.66 MPa·m^{1/2} of the pure TaC to 4.7 MPa·m^{1/2}. A similar increase in strength is also observed.

When MoSi_2 is used as sintering aid and SiC platelets formed after sintering (material TM-S), there was no improvement in toughness. Also for this composite, like for TS-S, the toughening due to crack deflection, see Fig. 11c, is counterbalanced by the tensile residual stress in the matrix. However, in this case, a drastic strength drop was measured. This is the result of the matrix grain coarsening and platelet agglomerations which acted as critical defects.

When Hi-Nicalon SiC fibers were added (material TT-HN), the crack proceeds straight through the fiber but it is deflected by the SiC platelets detached during sintering, Fig. 11d. The TaC matrix is under tensile residual stresses, however this composite was the toughest among those considered ($5.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$): its improvement with respect to pure TaC (T) is about 44% and of about 10% with respect to the starting matrix (TT). The fracture toughness value achieved well compares to the values measured for borides containing the same type of fiber [8,9]. For those chopped Hi-Nicalon fiber- ZrB_2 composites, crack pinning was supposed to be the main mechanism that justified the observed increases in toughness from 3.5 to $5.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ and overpassed the negative contribution given by residual stresses [8,9]. The strength of composite TT-HN is however lower than that of TT. Very likely the size of the reinforcement now represents the dimension of the critical defects.

Similarly, in the case of Tyranno SA3 (material TT-T), most of the times the fibers are cut across, however, if the fiber is arranged along the longitudinal direction of the advancing crack, the fissure hits the fiber, proceeds along the fiber/matrix boundary and circumvents it, see Fig. 11e. As overall result toughness doesn't change, $4.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, with respect to the starting matrix. The main difference between TT-HN and TT-T is the crystallinity degree of the reinforcement, as the final diameter of the fiber is nearly the same (about $7 \mu\text{m}$), Table 1. Since the toughness of TT-T did not change as compared to TT, we infer that the crystalline Tyranno SA3 must introduce more tension in the matrix compared to the Hi-Nicalon fibers. The estimations of the residual stresses reported in Fig. 10, are in fact based on the pristine values of the fiber. After sintering, however, they underwent different microstructural modification so that the final properties of the fiber are definitely modified with respect to the starting ones. A more refractory fiber, as the crystalline Tyranno SA3, has more chance to maintain properties closer to the initial values and it is very likely that the calculated residual tensile matrix stress is closer to the true value than in the case of Hi-Nicalon fiber which is strongly modified after the sintering process. In addition, Hi-Nicalon fiber debris transformed into particles may have induced further toughening through crack deflection mechanism in TT-HN. This kind of debris is not present in the case of Tyranno SA3.

When carbon fibers are added (material TS-C), the crack mostly goes around C fiber, Fig. 11f, but on the other side the graphite sheets and fragments spread among TaC grains weakens the overall microstructure, resulting in a null

toughness increment. In addition the CTE of the C fiber is even lower than that of SiC and very different from that of TaC, so additional thermal residual stresses develop and adversely affect the toughness by counterbalancing any toughening mechanism. The strength is much lower than the starting matrix TS due to large fiber dimension which act as fracture origin.

The plot in Fig. 12 shows the relationship between strength and toughness of the just presented materials with other TaC-based ceramics available in the literature characterized with the same CNB method and 4-point flexural strength [5]. It is apparent that TaC can achieve very high strength approaching 1 GPa, but in general the fracture toughness remains one key issue, as residual stress arising in the matrix upon introduction of these secondary phases prevents from notable improvements of the failure tolerance of these TaC-based composites.

5. Conclusions

In order to increase the fracture toughness of TaC, secondary phases were added: a transition metal disilicide, SiC in form of particles, platelets, and chopped fiber, or C short fibers. The microstructure of the ceramics and the evolution of the secondary phase added were studied by SEM and TEM and correlated to strength and fracture toughness.

A toughness increase was not always observed probably owing to the negative effect of thermal residual stresses, due to the introduction of lower CTE secondary phases. Conversely, high strength increase was obtained when SiC particles were added, approaching 1 GPa. TaSi₂ enabled a toughness increase up to 4.7 MPa·√m, owing to suitable tensional state arising in the composite, and strength around 680 MPa was measured. The highest toughness was found for addition of Hi-Nicalon fibers, 5.3 MPa·√m, coupled with a strength of 550 MPa. When Tyranno SA3 SiC fibers were introduced, no appreciable toughness increment was measured, again due to negative thermal residual stresses. The less favorable case was found for addition of C fiber that introduced too high tensile stress in the matrix and frustrated any positive contribution given by crack deflection and pinning if the fibers.

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Figures captions

Figure 1: SEM images of fibers used for TaC ceramics: a) Hi-Nicalon, b) Tyranno SA3, c) C fiber.

Figure 2: SEM images of a) pure TaC (T), b) TaC+Si₃N₄ (TS), c) TaC+Si₃N₄+SiC particles (TS-S), d) TaC+ TaSi₂ (TT). Black regions in a) are pores, whilst in b)-d) are SiC and SiO-based phases.

Figure 3: a) SEM image of platelets in TM-S and b)-c) TEM images of adjacent platelets. HR-TEM of d) SiC-SiC or e)-f) SiC-TaC interfaces.

Figure 4: a) SEM image of a fiber section in TT-HN and TEM images of b) fiber, c) fiber core with diffraction pattern showing the presence of amorphous phase, d) HR-TEM of the fiber core, e) particles dispersed in the rim, and f) SiC platelets around the fiber.

Figure 5: a) SEM image of a fiber section in TT-T and TEM images of b) fiber core and c) fiber rim with diffraction patterns showing similar cristallinity degree, d) HR-TEM of the fiber core, e) triple junction in the rim, and f) wetted interface between fiber and matrix.

Figure 6: a) SEM images of a fiber section in TS-C15 showing a) the overall morphology and b) a magnification of the fiber—matrix interface, arrows indicate graphite flakes. TEM images of c) fiber debris with diffraction pattern showing graphite reflections and d)-f) HR-TEM of the fiber-matrix interfaces. Arrows in b) point to graphite pockets.

Figure 7: SEM images of fracture surfaces of TaC-based materials containing a) platelets *TM-S*, b) Hi-Nicalon fiber *TT-HN*, c) Tyranno SA3 fiber *TT-T* and d) Carbon fiber *TS-C*.

Figure 8: Plots of a) CNB fracture toughness and b) 4-point flexural strength for TaC-based composites.

Figure 9: Sketch of the morphology evolution of platelets and fibers in the TaC-matrix during sintering. a) SiC platelet, b) Hi-Nicalon fiber, c) Tyranno SA3 fiber, d) C fiber.

Figure 10: Calculated thermal residual stresses in the TaC-based composites according to Taya et al.'s model [25] and $\Delta t=1400^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 11: SEM images of a slow advancing crack in: a) T, b) TS-S, c) TM-S, d) TT-HN, e) TT-T, f) TS-C. Arrows indicate crack deflection by particles, fibers or platelets.

Figure 12: Plot of fracture toughness and strength of TaC-based composites.

Tables

Table 1: Label, composition, sintering parameters, density, mean grain size (m.g.s.) and size of the reinforcing phases before and after sintering. HP: hot pressing, PS: pressureless sintering, AR: aspect ratio.

Label	Sint. add. (vol%)	Reinforce (vol%)	Reinforce size (μm)	Sintering ($^{\circ}\text{C}$,MPa,min)	Rel. density (%)	TaC m.g.s. (μm)	Reinforce after sintering (vol%)	Reinforce size after sintering (μm)
T	-	-	-	HP:1900,30,15	94.0	4.0 \pm 0.8	-	-
TS	5 Si ₃ N ₄	-	-	HP:1850,30,10	96.5	2.5 \pm 0.6	5 SiC	1.0
TS-S	5 Si ₃ N ₄	15 β -SiC	0.6	HP:1850,50,10	97.5	1.2 \pm 0.4	20 SiC	1.5
TT	-	15 TaSi ₂	2.0	HP:1750,30,10	97.1	2.5 \pm 0.5	10 TaSi ₂	3-8
TM-S	5 MoSi ₂	15 β -SiC	0.6	PS:2100,-,180,Ar	96.5	7.8 \pm 2.8	15 SiC _{pl}	AR: 1.8
TT-HN	10 TaSi ₂	20 SiC Hi-Nicalon	\varnothing : 15, l=500	HP:1750,30,8	98.1	2.5 \pm 0.7	15 SiC Hi-Nicalon + 5SiC _{pl}	\varnothing : 7.0, l=80, AR: 2.5
TT-T	10 TaSi ₂	15 SiC Tyranno SA3	\varnothing : 7.5, l=200	HP:1700,40,9	97.9	2.4 \pm 0.7	15 SiC Tyranno SA3	\varnothing : 7.5, l=200
TS-C	5 Si ₃ N ₄	20 Cfiber	\varnothing : 7.0, l=200	HP:1900,50,12	97.8	0.6 \pm 0.2	15 Cfiber + 5 SiC	\varnothing : 6.2, l=200, 1.5